

CONNECTED DOMSATURATION NUMBER OF A GRAPH

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Abstract:

In general, a set S of vertices of a graph G is said to be saturated by an m atching M (where a matching M in G is a set of independent edges) if every vertex of S is incident to some edge of M . In domsaturation the concept of domination is introduced. The domsaturation number, ds of a graph G is defined to be the least positive integer k such that every vertex of G lies in a dominating set of cardinality k . A graph G consists of a pair $(V(G), E(G))$ where $V(G)$ is a non-empty finite set whose elements are called points or vertices and $E(G)$ is a set of unordered pairs of distinct elements of $V(G)$. The elements of $E(G)$ are called lines or edges of the graph G . A graph with p points and q lines is called a (p, q) graph.

Key Words: Number of Graph, Connected Graphs, etc.,

Introduction:

Within last thirty years parallel to the growth of Computer Science, Electrical and Computer Engineering and operations Research, Graph Theory is also exhibiting explosive growth. The fastest-growing area within graph theory is the study of domination in graphs. In this paper, an attempt is made to develop a concept in domination called the domsaturation number of a graph. In general, a set S of vertices of a graph G is said to be saturated by an m atching M (where a matching M in G is a set of independent edges) if every vertex of S is incident to some edge of M . In domsaturation the concept of domination is introduced. The domsaturation number, ds of a graph G is defined to be the least positive integer k such that every vertex of G lies in a dominating set of cardinality k .

Preliminaries:

Definition 1.1:

A graph G consists of a pair $(V(G), E(G))$ where $V(G)$ is a non-empty finite set whose elements are called points or vertices and $E(G)$ is a set of unordered pairs of distinct elements of $V(G)$. The elements of $E(G)$ are called lines or edges of the graph G . A graph with p points and q lines is called a (p, q) graph.

Example 1.1:

Let $V = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $E = \{\{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}\}$ $G = (V, E)$ is a $(4, 3)$ graph. This graph can be represented by the diagram given in Figure 1.

Fig 1

Definition 1.2:

If $x = \{u, v\} \in E(G)$, the line x is said to join u and v . We write $x = uv$ and we say that the points u and v are adjacent. We also say that the point u and the line x are incident with each other. If two distinct lines x and y are incident with a common point then they are called adjacent lines.

Example 1.2:

Let $V = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ and $E = \{\{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{1, 4\}, \{2, 3\}, \{2, 4\}, \{3, 4\}\}$. This graph is represented by the diagram in Figure 2. In the diagram a, b, c, d, e, f represent the edges in E . Fig 2

Fig 2

The line b joins the points 1 and 3 and hence the vertices 1 and 3 are adjacent.
 The line b is incident with 1 as well as 3.
 The lines b and c are called adjacent lines as they have 1 as a common point.

Domsaturation Number of a Graph:

Definition 2.1:

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. A subset S of V is called a dominating set if every vertex in $V - S$ is adjacent to at least one vertex in S . The domination number γ of G is the minimum cardinality of a dominating set in G .

Example 2.1:

Consider the graph

Fig 1

For this graph $S_1 = \{1,3,5\}$, $S_2 = \{3,6,7,8\}$, $S_3 = \{2,4,6,7,8\}$ are some of the dominating sets.
 The domination number $\gamma(G) = 3$ since $\{1,3,5\}$ is a dominating set of minimum cardinality.

Definition 2.2:

The maximum order of a partition of V into dominating sets of G is called the domatic number of G and is denoted by d .

Example 2.2:

Consider the graph

Fig 2

For this graph $\{\{1\}, \{2,3\}, \{4,5\}\}$, $\{\{1\}, \{2,3,4,5\}\}$, $\{\{2,5\}, \{3,4\}, \{1\}\}$ are some of the partitions of V into dominating sets. The domatic number $d(G) = 3$ since $\{\{1\}, \{2, 5\}, \{3, 4\}\}$ is a maximum order partition of V into dominating sets of G . In particular, $d(K_n) = n$

Definition 2.3:

A graph G is said to be domatically full if $d = \delta + 1$ where δ is the minimum degree of a vertex in G .

Example 2.3:

Consider the graph

Fig 3

For this graph $\delta = 2$ and $d(G) = 3$
 (ie) $d = 2 + 1 = \delta + 1$
 $\therefore G$ is domatically full.

Connected Domsaturation Number of a Graph:

Definition 3.1:

The connected domsaturation number ds_c of a connected graph $G = (V, E)$ is the least positive integer k such that every vertex of G lies in a connected dominating set of cardinality k .

Example 3.1:

Consider the graph

Fig 1

For this graph $ds_c = 3$ since $\{ 1,3,5 \}$, $\{ 2,3,5 \}$, $\{ 4,3,5 \}$, $\{ 7,3,5 \}$, $\{ 8,3,5 \}$ and $\{ 3,5,6 \}$ are connected dominating sets of cardinality 3 containing all the vertices of G and 3 is the least positive integer with this property. Let C_n and P_n denote the cycle and the path on n -vertices.

Note 3.1:

- $ds_c(k_n) = 1$
- $ds_c(c_n) = n - 2$
- $ds_c(p_n) = n - 1$

Result 3.1:

For any graph G such that G and \bar{G} are connected $\gamma_c + \bar{\gamma}_c \leq p+1$ and equality holds iff $G \cong c_5$

Result 3.2:

For any graph G such that G and \bar{G} are connected, $\gamma_c + \bar{\gamma}_c = p$ iff $G \cong c_p$ ($p \geq 6$), P_p ($p \geq 4$), or the graph G_1 , given in Fig.2.

Fig 2

Result 3.3:

For any connected (p,q) graph G with maximum degree Δ , $\lfloor \frac{p}{\Delta+1} \rfloor \leq \gamma_c(G) \leq 2q-p$. The lower bound is attained iff G has a vertex of degree $p - 1$ and the upper bound is attained iff G is a path.

Result 3.4:

Let G be a connected graph of order $p \geq 4$ such that both G and \bar{G} are connected. Then $\gamma_c + \bar{\gamma}_c \leq p - 3$. The bound is attained iff G is P_4 .

Note 3.2:

If V is the vertex set of G and S is a γ_c - set of G , then for any vertex $u \in V - S$, $S \cup \{u\}$ is a connected dominating set and hence it follows that $ds_c = \gamma_c$ or $\gamma_c + 1$.

Definition 3.2:

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a connected graph and let $v \in V$. Then vertex v is said to be γ_c - totally free if v does not lie in any γ_c - set of G .

Example 3.2:

In a tree any pendant vertex is γ_c - totally free since no γ_c - set contains a pendant vertex.

Definition 3.3:

The vertex v is said to be γ_c - free if there exist γ_c - sets A and B such that $v \in A$ and $v \notin B$.

Example 3.3:

In a complete graph, every vertex is γ_c - free. For a complete graph K_n , $\{u\}$ is a γ_c - Set for any arbitrary vertex u of K_n . Hence every vertex is γ_c - free.

Definition 3.4:

The vertex v is said to be γ_c - fixed if v lies in every γ_c - set of G .

Example 3.4:

In a tree every non-pendant vertex is γ_c - fixed. Since $\langle \gamma_c \rangle$ is connected and γ_c dominates all the pendant vertices, every non-pendant vertex lie in every γ_c - set of trees.

Conclusion:

The domsaturation ds of a graph $G=(V,E)$ is the least positive integer k such that every vertex of G lies in a dominating set of cardinality k . we obtain several result connecting ds and other graph theoretic parameters. We also characterize certain classes of graph for which $ds=\gamma$. The connected domsaturation number of ds_c of a graph $G=(V,E)$ is the least positive integer k such that every vertex of G lies in a connected dominating set of cardinality k .

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